

THE MAIN FACTORS AFFECTING OF UZBEKISTAN AND CENTRAL ASIAN COUNTRIES TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF ART

¹Abdullaev Akbar Hikmatovich, ²Bobomurodova Sojida Abloqulovna

¹Head of the Department, Navoi state pedagogical institute

²Master's student, Navoi state pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7768234>

Abstract. *This article discusses the history of visual art of Uzbekistan and Central Asian countries and the period and principles of statehood that influenced its unique development, as well as the development of visual art in today's new Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *culture, art, evolution, spirituality, complex, enlightenment, material, values, treasure, carving, painting, pottery.*

Objective study and explanation of the long and complex cultural and spiritual life of the peoples of Central Asia from the earliest times to the present day is an important task of today. It consists in researching all the processes related to the joint activity of man with nature and society, as well as the spiritual life of people. Culture refers to the complex of material and spiritual wealth created by the creative activity of people. The term culture has various meanings in modern scientific literature. In Latin, it means "to work, to take care of", and later it is used in the sense of "to be enlightened, to be educated, to be educated". The term "culture" that is often used in the Uzbek language means "civilization" in Arabic. Culture is the "environment created by man", the set of material and spiritual values created by mankind, which enriches human activity. A society without culture. as it is not, culture does not exist outside of society. Crime creates culture. When society is rich, culture also rises. Individuals do not have separate culture. Individuals live in the cultural environment of a particular society and their culture is formed.

The evolution of culture and art, on the one hand, and the development of the statehood of Uzbekistan, on the other hand, testify to the continuity and interconnectedness of this historical process.

The current appearance of certain culture, especially fine arts, corresponds to a certain stage of the development of statehood. The analysis of available data allows us to distinguish several periods in the history of culture and art of Uzbekistan in the sense of the development of statehood.

Islamic religion and civilization, which entered the region in the VII-VIII centuries, in the IX-XI centuries not only changed the socio-economic urban planning structure of the local city, but also changed its architectural image, but also had a strong influence on its philosophy. As the image of medieval Muslim cities appeared more in places of worship, mosques, madrasas, minarets, etc., their interior and exterior decorations began to differ radically from European fine art. These brought a new fluidity and logical expression to the general atmosphere of city life. Bricks were used for construction, and wood and concrete were used for decoration. Of course, this includes carpentry, carving, painting, pottery, etc. created a solid ground for the development of art forms. In the 9th - 12th centuries, a new method of decoration was formed and developed, which laid the foundation for the art of the Islamic Middle Ages. Decorative art replaces visual culture and remains one of the foundations of Muslim culture. Within the framework of pan-

Islamic art, Central Asia's own aesthetic art was formed between two rivers, and it is more related to the statehood and socio-political development of Movarunnahr, the basis of the future territory of Uzbekistan.

One of the most important periods of development of the next visual art is certainly the period of Amir Temur and the Timurids. It is known from history that the emergence and development of the kingdom of Amir Temur and his successors was an extraordinary cultural and historical reality in the world cultural development. The state structures within the framework of the Timurid's kingdom go far beyond the boundaries of the territories of present-day Uzbekistan. During the period of Amir Temur and the Timurids, culture and art reach their peak and are rightfully called the Timurid Renaissance. It is at this time that art appears as a bright symbol of patronage by a powerful state and at the same time as an expression of the philosophy of a powerful kingdom.

Although the representatives of the Timurid dynasty strongly believed in Islamic beliefs, secularism in art was clearly expressed. The leading areas of culture and art, architecture, handicrafts and miniature paintings express the powerful ideas of the state and its leading role in the field of science, enlightenment and art. Arts and crafts are considered the most important indicator and sign of a developed state system.

The art of the independent state of Uzbekistan, the ideas of national independence and the aspiration of our country to find a place in the world community were expressed in many types of culture and art, as well as in the architecture of Tashkent, just like in the time of the Timurids. It is here that a unique two-way style emerges. In addition to buildings using national forms (the Supreme Council, Tashkent City Hall, the buildings of the Timurid History Museum, etc.), buildings oriented to world architectural practices have risen in the capital (the Intercontinental Complex, Sheraton Hotel, Bank Association building). Many measures adopted by the state during the years of independence were aimed at supporting theater, music, visual arts, cinematography and other artistic creations, which are a testimony to the new development of the relationship between the state and culture. is giving.

Today, the state is the main patron of art in Uzbekistan. At the same time, creative freedom has been and will remain a leading and founding principle in the field of art and culture.

REFERENCES

1. CULTURAL AND ART HISTORY OF UZBEKISTAN Tashkent "Uzbekistan Trade Publishing House of Printing Press"
2. Инояттов С.И. «Кармана в очерках истории» Шарк 2006
3. Мухаммаджонов А.Р. «Древняя Бухара» Ташкент, 1991.
4. ГЎЗАЛЛИК ФАЛСАФАСИ – Тошкент, 2008 й. С. Булатов, Н. Толипов.
5. THE USE OF CREAM IN THE SCIENCE OF SCIENTIFIC TOPICS IN GRADES 1-4 OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS - ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. -ISSN: 2249-7137 Vol. 11, Issue 11, November 2021 Rustamov A. M
6. Sh. U. Bobonazarov. "Rangtasvir" Study guide. Navoi 20228. 8. Методические аспекты преподавания общетехнических дисциплин в профессиональных образовательных организациях. Материалы VIII Международной научно-практической конференции «профессиональное образование проблемы и достижения» 4–5 декабря 2018 г 7 (495) 544-2494 support@elibrary.ru

7. Абдуллаев Акбар Хикматович НРАВСТВЕННОЕ И ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ВОСПИТАНИЕ УЧЕНИКОВ ЧЕРЕЗ ИЗОБРАЗИТЕЛЬНОЕ ИСКУССТВО // Academy. 2021. №4 (67). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nravstvennoe-i-esteticheskoe-vospitanie-uchenikov-cherez-izobrazitelnoe-iskusstvo> (дата обращения: 04.03.2023).